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AWARENESS AND ADOPTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS AMONG ECONOMICS STUDENTS IN A TERTIARY INSTITUTION, KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined Awareness and Adoption of Artificial Intelligence Tools among Economics Students in a Tertiary Institution in Kaduna state. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The study population comprised one hundred (137) Economics students from Federal University of Education, Zaria, 2024/2025 academic session. A sample of 108 students was drawn using simple random sampling. The questionnaire titled Awareness and Adoption of Artificial Intelligence Tools among Economic Students (AAAITQ) was the instrument used for data collection. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire were established. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.79. The percentage and mean were used for data analysis. The results of this study revealed that students demonstrated a moderate to high level of awareness of AI tools such as ChatGPT, though peer and lecturer discussions about AI remain limited. Results also revealed a high level of adoption and consistent use of AI tools, particularly ChatGPT, among Economics students, although institutional or lecturer encouragement is still lacking. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the university should organise regular workshops and seminars to enhance both students' and lecturers' awareness and practical knowledge of AI tools for academic purposes. Also, lecturers should be encouraged and supported to integrate AI-based platforms like ChatGPT into teaching and learning activities to improve student engagement and performance.

Keywords: Awareness, Adoption, Artificial Intelligence, Economics, Students, Tertiary Institution.

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INTRODUCTION

The advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has ushered in a new era of technological advancement, characterized by groundbreaking innovations and transformative potential across various sectors, including education (Agbo et al., 2023). AI encompasses machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, and robotics, among other advanced technologies, which collectively have the capacity to redefine traditional practices and frameworks (UNESCO, 2022). Globally, AI-powered tools and platforms are reshaping how students learn, how educators teach, and how universities operate. The deployment of intelligent tutoring systems, adaptive learning software, and automated administrative processes exemplifies the disruptive influence of AI in education. AI presents a viable solution to these issues by automating administrative tasks, optimizing resource use, and enabling data-driven decisions. Its

advanced capabilities surpass conventional methods through the automation of repetitive processes, large-scale data analysis, and the provision of actionable insights (Awofiranye, 2024). It can monitor and predict student performance trends, enabling timely interventions for learners who require additional support (Adelana & Akinyemi, 2021). Furthermore, AI boosts efficiency by streamlining grading, automating attendance records, and optimizing timetable scheduling, ultimately reducing teacher workload and allowing greater focus on instructional delivery.

Beyond its administrative capabilities, Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a pivotal role in personalized learning by tailoring instructional content to suit the unique needs of individual students. AI-powered intelligent tutoring systems offer real-time feedback, design customized study plans, and create interactive learning environments that

promote deeper student engagement (Olatunde-Aiyedun, 2024). In developed countries, the integration of AI in educational management has significantly enhanced institutional efficiency, enabled data-driven decision-making and improved student performance. Considering Nigeria's growing student population, persistent teacher shortages, and challenges in effective resource allocation, AI provides a promising avenue to close these gaps, strengthen school governance, and elevate the quality of education (Fullan et al., 2023). For Nigerian university students, AI presents both opportunities and challenges. The nation is at a critical juncture, grappling with pervasive issues such as inadequate infrastructure, brain drain, and high unemployment rates among graduates (Olaleye & Hassan, 2022). At the same time, it must confront the demands of an increasingly digitised and automated global economy. Leveraging AI could offer innovative solutions to these long-standing problems, enabling universities to enhance educational delivery, bridge the skills gap, and improve graduate employability (Agbo et al., 2023).

Building on the discussion of AI's capacity to personalise learning and strengthen institutional efficiency, Economics, a discipline grounded in systematic reasoning and quantitative analysis, faces significant pedagogical challenges in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Despite its scientific orientation, instruction in Economics often remains traditional, hindered by outdated curricula, limited access to modern learning materials, and insufficient exposure to practical data-analysis tools, which together impede students' ability to apply theoretical concepts to real-world economic problems. In this context, AI technologies such as intelligent tutoring systems and interactive simulations offer promising interventions by rendering abstract concepts tangible, providing personalized instructional pathways, and cultivating essential data-driven skills for economic modelling, forecasting, and analysis. However, many Nigerian undergraduates demonstrate only moderate awareness of AI's broader educational potential, commonly recognizing AI through virtual assistants rather than as a suite of

pedagogical tools; this limited literacy constrains students' capacity to exploit AI for research and quantitative analysis and underscores the need for targeted AI integration in economics curricula to bridge the digital skills gap and align instruction with contemporary labour-market demands.

The increasing emphasis on AI integration in education, highlighted by the Tribune (2024) and supported by the Federal Ministry of Education (2023) through the National Digital Learning Policy, underscores the need for Economics students to develop strong AI competencies. AI tools are vital because they enhance data analysis, support understanding of complex economic concepts through simulations, and provide personalised academic assistance. Sule (2024) notes that AI can significantly improve learning efficiency and student engagement by analysing performance data and generating customised feedback, an advantage for Economics students who often struggle with topics such as elasticity, econometric modelling, monetary policy, and fiscal analysis. As Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014) emphasised, AI is transforming global industries, making AI literacy increasingly essential for Economics students whose future careers intersect with digital technology, automation, and data science. Scholars such as Cheng (2019), Luckin et al. (2016), and Ogunyemi (2020) also highlight that AI fosters critical thinking, innovation, and personalised learning, leading to improved academic performance. Although developed countries have widely adopted AI-driven platforms such as adaptive learning systems and intelligent tutors, adoption in Nigeria remains limited due to infrastructure and personnel constraints (Ajayi & Ogunleye, 2021). Nonetheless, studies like Ogunyemi et al. (2020) affirm that Nigerian students stand to benefit greatly from AI-enabled personalised learning, while Nguyen et al. (2024) show that although tools like ChatGPT are increasingly used for learning and academic tasks, concerns persist regarding overreliance, reduced critical thinking, ethical issues, and academic dishonesty. In response to these opportunities and challenges, the study investigates the awareness and adoption of AI tools among

Economics students at the Federal University of Education, Zaria.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education has transformed how students learn, interact with content, and solve academic challenges. AI-driven tools such as AI tutors and conversational agents like ChatGPT are increasingly being used to supplement traditional teaching methods, offering students instant access to explanations, personalized feedback, and academic support. However, despite these technological advancements, there seems to be low awareness in understanding how effectively these tools are being adopted and utilized by economics students in Nigerian tertiary institutions, particularly at the Federal University of Education, Zaria. Many students are either unaware of the full capabilities of AI tools or lack the digital literacy required to use them efficiently. In addition, the absence of institutional strategies to formally integrate AI into the learning process may limit the potential benefits of these technologies.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence tools, particularly AI tutors and ChatGPT, among Economics students at the Federal University of Education, Zaria.
2. assess the extent of adoption and usage patterns of AI tools in the academic activities of Economics students at the Federal University of Education, Zaria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence tools, particularly AI tutors and ChatGPT, among Economics students at the Federal University of Education, Zaria?
2. What is the extent of adoption and usage patterns of AI tools in the academic activities of Economics students at the Federal University of Education, Zaria?

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The study population comprised one hundred (137) Economics students from Federal University of Education, Zaria, 2024/2025 academic session. A sample of 108 students was drawn using simple random sampling. The sample was drawn according to the recommendations of the Research Advisors Table (2006). The questionnaire tagged Awareness and Adoption of Artificial Intelligence Tools among Economic Students (AAAIQ) was the instrument used for data collection. It comprised fourteen items (14), four-point modified Likert-scaled statements. The instrument was subjected to expert validation by lecturers from the Faculty of Education. Through this, necessary corrections and observations were made with a view to making it better for appropriate data collection in this study. All corrections and observations made were harmonised and effected to make the item a valid tool for data collection in this study. Cronbach's alpha was used to establish the internal consistency of the instrument. A reliability coefficient of 0.79 was found. The instrument was administered by the researcher to the respondents over a period of two weeks. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used for data analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1: Level of Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Tools

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I am familiar with the concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education.	35	40	15	10	3.00	0.95	Accepted
2	I have heard about AI-powered learning tools such as AI tutors.	30	38	20	12	2.86	0.98	Accepted
3	I am aware that ChatGPT is an example of an AI tool used in academics.	45	35	10	10	3.15	0.96	Accepted
4	I understand how AI tutors' function in supporting students' learning.	20	35	30	15	2.60	0.97	Accepted
5	My lecturers or peers have discussed or introduced AI tools in academic settings.	18	30	32	20	2.46	1.00	Rejected
6	I have seen or read about the use of AI tools in economics education.	25	40	25	10	2.80	0.93	Accepted
7	I believe AI tools like ChatGPT can play a role in enhancing academic performance.	50	35	10	5	3.30	0.84	Accepted
Cumulative mean						2.90	0.95	

Table 1 revealed that students demonstrated a moderate to high level of awareness of AI tools such as ChatGPT (Mean = 2.90, SD = 0.95), though peer and lecturer discussions about AI remain limited.

Table 2: Extent of Adoption and Usage Patterns of AI Tools

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
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1	I have personally used ChatGPT or other AI tools to assist with my economics coursework.	40	35	15	10	3.05	0.97	Accepted
2	I regularly use AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, AI tutors) to understand complex economic concepts.	28	32	25	15	2.73	1.03	Accepted
3	AI tools have become a part of my study routine.	22	30	30	18	2.56	1.02	Accepted
4	I use ChatGPT or similar AI platforms for academic writing or assignment help.	38	34	18	10	3.00	0.98	Accepted
5	I have received guidance or encouragement to use AI tools for academic purposes.	15	25	35	25	2.30	1.00	Rejected
6	I find AI tools more helpful than traditional study materials for learning economics.	26	36	25	13	2.75	0.98	Accepted
7	I plan to continue using AI tools to support my academic work in the future.	45	40	10	5	3.25	0.83	Accepted
Cumulative mean						2.81	0.97	

Table 2 indicates a moderate to high level of adoption and consistent use of AI tools, particularly ChatGPT (Mean = 2.81, Std. dev = 0.97), among Economics students, although institutional or lecturer encouragement is still lacking.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study in Table 1 revealed that students demonstrated a moderate to high level of awareness of AI tools such as ChatGPT (Mean = 2.90, SD = 0.95), though peer and lecturer discussion about AI remains limited. This finding corroborates that of Alimi et al. (2021) conducted a study to explore university students' awareness, access to, and use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies, revealing a generally moderate level of awareness among students. The findings indicate that while most students could recognise popular AI-driven virtual assistants such as Google Assistant, Alexa, and Oliva, their understanding of AI as a broader technological concept, especially its relevance to education and learning was limited. This lack of awareness suggests that although AI tools are increasingly integrated into everyday digital experiences, their potential applications for academic enhancement remain underexplored by students.

The results in Table 2 also revealed a high level of adoption and consistent use of AI tools, particularly ChatGPT, among Economics students (Mean = 2.81, SD = 0.97), although institutional or lecturer encouragement is still lacking. This finding

agrees with that of Luckin et al (2016), who found that AI adoption in higher education offers numerous benefits, such as personalised learning, enhanced academic performance, and improved administrative efficiency. Similarly, Ogunyemi (2020) opined that for Nigerian students, understanding AI's potential can help them utilise tools that support academic growth and research productivity, especially in the context of resource constraints. Regarding institutional or lecturer encouragement lacking, Nguyen et al (2024) found that ChatGPT is widely adopted by students for learning and information searches, with many also finding it reliable for academic tasks such as idea generation and assignment completion. However, concerns about overreliance were noted, which may hinder independent thinking and critical evaluation skills. Issues related to academic dishonesty, reduced creativity and ethical problems such as plagiarism and information security were also identified.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that Economics students at the Federal University of Education, Zaria, possess a moderate to high level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence tools such as ChatGPT. Most students acknowledged AI's potential to enhance learning and academic performance. However, limited discussion and guidance from lecturers or peers suggest gaps in institutional promotion of AI literacy. Findings further indicated a growing trend in students' personal adoption and routine use of AI for coursework and research activities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, it is recommended that:

1. The Federal University of Education should organise regular workshops and seminars to enhance awareness and practical knowledge of AI tools for academic purposes.
2. Economics students should be encouraged and supported to integrate AI-based platforms like ChatGPT into their learning activities to improve their engagement and performance.

REFERENCES

- Adelana, O.P. & Akinyemi, A.L. (2021). Artificial intelligence-based tutoring systems utilisation for learning: a survey of senior secondary students' awareness and readiness in Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State. *UNIZIK Journal of Education Research & Policy Studies*, 9(1), 16-28.
- Agbo, F.J., Sanusi, I.T., & Onyeka, C.N. (2023). Artificial intelligence and education in Africa: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 1(4), 5-14.
- Ajayi, T. & Ogunleye, O. (2021). The role of artificial intelligence in advancing higher education in Nigeria: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal Educational Technology*, 12(3), 45-56.
- Alimi, A.E., Buraimoh, O.F., Aladesusi, G.A. & Babalola, E.O. (2021). University Students' Awareness of, Access to, and Use of Artificial Intelligence for Learning in Kwara State. *Indonesian Journal of Teaching in Science*, 1(2), 91-104.
- Awofiranye, M. (2024). The challenges of using AI in education. Available from <https://www.afterschoolafrica.com/78994/the-challenges-of-using-ai-in-education>.
- Bayere, R.A., Michael, S., Agu, B. & Oloruntoba, T.D. (2025). A Broken Pipeline: From School to Nowhere, Rethinking Nigeria's Education-to-Employment Transition. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5470890>
- Brynjolfsson, E., & McAfee, A. (2014). *The second machine age: Work, progress, and prosperity in a time of brilliant technologies*. W.W. Norton & Company.
- Cheng, J. (2019). The role of AI in education. *The International Journal of Educational Research*, 98, 45-55.
- Federal Ministry of Education. (2023). National Digital Learning Policy. Abuja: Federal Ministry of Education.
- Fullan, M., Azorín, C., Harris, A. & Jones, M. (2023). Artificial intelligence and school leadership: challenges, opportunities and implications. *School Leadership and Management*, 1(1), 56-67.
- Jonathan, A.E., Osaretinmwun, A.G. & Onanore, E.F. (2025). Awareness, Availability, and Integration of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Academic and Research Tasks among Lecturers at Delta State College of Education, Mosogar. *International Journal of Innovative Information Systems & Technology Research*, 13(2), 163-173.
- Luckin, R., Holmes, W., Griffiths, M., & Forcier, L.B. (2016). *Intelligence unleashed: An argument for AI in education*. Pearson Education.
- Nguyen, T.N.T., Lai, N.V. & Nguyen, Q.T. (2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) in education: A case study on ChatGPT's influence on student learning behaviours. *Educational Process International Journal* 13(2), 105-121.
- Ogunyemi, L., Ajayi, B. & Adebajo, O. (2020). The potential of AI-driven tools in Nigerian higher education. *International Journal of Learning Technology*, 15(4), 56-72.
- Ogunyemi, O. (2020). AI adoption in Nigerian higher education: Opportunities and challenges. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(2), 34-47.
- Olaleye, S.A. & Hassan, M.T. (2022). Digital transformation in Nigerian universities: The role of AI and machine learning. *African Journal of Innovation and Development*, 13(3), 81-95.

- Olatunde-Aiyedun, T.G. (2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) in education: integration of AI into science education curriculum in Nigerian universities. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Digit*, 1(1), 14-24.
- Salahudeen, L.A. & Abraham, O.A. (2018). The Effect of Teaching Method of Economics on Student Performance: A Case Study of Selected Secondary Schools in Ojo Local Government Area, Nigeria. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 2(4), 109-119.
- Sule, J. (2024). The Cable online Newspaper. <https://www.thecable.ng/integrating-artificial-intelligence-into-education-in-nigeria/>
- Tribune Newspaper (2024). Expert urges Nigerian varsities to embrace AI for academic transformation. p11. <https://tribuneonlineng.com/expert-urges-nigerian-varsities-to-embrace-ai-for-academic-transformation/>
- UNESCO. (2022). Artificial Intelligence in Education: Addressing challenges and enhancing learning outcomes. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation. <https://www.unesco.org>.